

Examining the Core Behavioral and Leadership Competencies of School Heads for Enhancing Professional Development

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ABSTRACT

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To thrive today, school leaders must cultivate competencies that respond effectively to real-world challenges. This study examines the core behavioral and leadership competencies of identified school heads as basis for the development of a guidebook to enhance their professional development. The descriptive qualitative design was used to gather the school head's leadership competencies, describe the induction programs attended and their experiences, and develop a guidebook to enhance their behavioral and leadership competencies. Results showed that exposure to the induction program greatly improves the leadership competencies of the school heads. Attendance to training supports school heads in translating their knowledge into a more visible and effective recognition of it as part of their leadership identity. However, the study also found out that the induction program showed inconsistency in terms of opportunity, timing, program naming, content delivery, and strengthened mentorship. Based on these findings, the study suggests institutionalizing the use of this guidebook to cater to inclusion and serve as a complementary tool to the school head's induction program to enhance leadership competencies. The study also proposes to explore a localized induction program, such as a district level, bridge the gap of inclusion to provide need-based content and conduct a future study on the long-term effects of the guidebook in enhancing the core behavioral and leadership competencies of school heads.

KEYWORDS:

core behavioral competencies, guidebook, leadership competencies, professional development

1. INTRODUCTION

School heads lead the path of organizational success, which requires skills that go beyond concepts and theories. The school head's leadership competencies set the ground for school leadership that should be an adherence to the national competency standards. These competencies should emphasize professional development, mentoring, and capacity-building, which are necessary to strengthen school leadership and improve instructional quality. The core behavioral and leadership competencies of school heads have a direct impact on school administration, accountability, and the quality of the educational delivery (Enriquez, 2026). These competencies are interdependent; both are required to attain leadership success. The correlation between competence and performance, ethical leadership, supervisory

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competence, and democratic or transformational leadership behaviors are linked to improved governance and more efficient school functioning (Alagos, 2024).

The school heads' leadership competencies are the foundation of school management; the core behavioral competencies demonstrate the functional capabilities of school heads reflected in their day-to-day leadership behaviors. It set the actual delivery of school leadership aligned with the expected core behavioral practices. While the leadership competencies hold developed skills that address the changing requirements of educational leadership. The competencies are anchored on planning, supervision, collaboration, and school improvement rather than solitary skills. Moreover, España (2025) identified communication, confidence, and professional support as the key elements of the development of a leader. These leadership competencies should be molded in an early stage of leadership to ensure readiness and avoid leadership experimentation (Ortiz et al. 2025).

According to Bagiw (2025), the school heads' induction program provides the opportunity for leadership development and improvement aligned in the mandate of the

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Philippine Professional Standards of School Heads (PPSSH). The program caters to the core behavioral and leadership heads, who are anticipated to oversee and, of course, to encourage and assist teachers. School heads' induction program ought to be regarded as a process and not a one-time endeavor because they influence the way school heads lead, communicate, build competencies of the school heads, and harmonize the five key domains of the PPSSH. Through this program school heads strengthen coaching, performance control, and self- and other development, which are vital areas of leadership, and school heads are anticipated to oversee and, of course, to encourage and assist teachers. School heads' induction programs ought to be regarded as a process and not a one-time endeavor because it influences the way school heads lead, communicate, supervise, and improve others. Moreover, the induction training provides school leaders with management skills and professional attitudes, hence being an important facilitator of leadership development.

However, even with the rich literature regarding this study, gaps were noted specifically in the school leadership competencies. Extensive literature focuses on the induction program attended, but few examine the content and availability of the program among school heads. Inconsistent delivery of the program among school heads was noted; its intention to bridge the gap from instructional skill to school management creates disparity. This study will bridge the gap of consistency and opportunity through a guidebook development that is complementary to the school head's induction program. The respondents are the school heads of the Municipality of Donsol, both from public elementary and secondary schools, who attended the school heads' induction program. Excluded are the non-attendees of school heads' induction programs, both private and elementary teachers, and other school personnel.

This research aimed to explore the core behavioral and leadership competencies of school heads for enhancing their professional development. Specifically, it aims to (1) identify the school heads' leadership competencies in terms of core behavioral and leadership competencies; (2) describe the induction programs attended by the school heads; (3) describe the experiences of the school heads in the application of the induction program; and (4) develop a guidebook for enhancing the core competencies of school heads.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research used a descriptive qualitative research design to comprehensively explore the school head's induction program and the experiences of the informants (Sandelowski, 2000). This allows the development of a guidebook for enhancing the core behavioral and leadership competencies of school heads.

The Participants

The study utilized purposive sampling, a total of 11 participants, seven elementary and four secondary school

heads—from the municipality of Donsol. As participants in the school head's induction program, these individuals served as key informants capable of providing firsthand insights into their leadership profiles, induction programs attended, and experiences in induction program applications.

The Instrument

To achieve the goal of establishing the leadership profile of the school heads, the 11 school heads have been interviewed through a validated researcher-made questionnaire. The demographic part of the instrument comprises the items like position, length of service, education level, and other relevant professional data, as well as the signs associated with the leadership profile. The semi-structured interview guide was used to collect the school head's experiences and practices.

Data Collection

The researchers ensured ethical compliance before proceeding with data collection. The research data was collected between 28 November 2025 and 13 February 2026. Before proceeding with the empirical work, the researcher seeks the necessary approvals and authorizations of the concerned authorities. An official form of request for permission was secured to the respective offices and school authorities in the Donsol District. Upon getting authorization, the researcher liaises with the school heads involved to find out the time, accessibility, and modalities of collecting the data and prepares the approved instruments, informed consent forms, and other supporting materials that the study needs.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the data, descriptive analysis was employed, and frequency and percentage were used to determine the leadership profiles of school heads in terms of core behavioral and leadership competencies and describe the induction programs. The frequency determines the uniformity or inconsistency of some answers. Percentages indicated the top and bottom competency indicators, hence guiding on priority areas of the guidebook. Thematic analysis of the qualitative data was used for the third objective, which described the experiences of school heads in applying the induction program. The combined findings, whose source was surveys and interviews, were used for the fourth objective, which is to develop a guidebook to build core competencies of school heads and involve the creation of a guidebook.

III. RESULTS

This section presents results of the study. The presentation of the data includes the following topics: the school head's leadership profile in terms of core behavioral and leadership competencies; the induction program attended by the school heads; experiences of the school heads in the induction program; and developing a guidebook.

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School Head’s Leadership Competencies

To establish a comprehensive leadership competency of the school heads, the analysis focused on two domains: core behavioral competencies and leadership competencies.

Table 1: School Head’s Core Behavioral Competencies

CORE BEHAVIORAL COMPETENCIES	Frequency (f) (n=11)	Percentage
Self-management	10	91 %
Professionalism & ethics	10	91 %
Result focus	10.2	92.8%
Teamwork	10.2	92.8 %
Service orientation	10	91 %
Innovations	10	91 %

Results in Table 1 showed that among the six indicators of the core behavioral competencies, two of which garnered 92.8% in the school heads' ratings, which are the result focus and teamwork. While the four remaining indicators garnered 91%, namely, self-management, professional ethics, service, and innovations. For this study, the results highlight that exposure to the induction program greatly improves the core behavioral competencies of the school heads. Attendance to training supports school heads in translating their knowledge into a more visible and effective recognition of it as part of their leadership identity. The results yield that the informant’s applications of the required behaviors were evident and well developed. The slight difference of scores on the core behavioral competencies implies that almost all school heads have the same professional and behavioral maturity.

Table 2: School Head’s Leadership Competencies

LEADERSHIP COMPETENCIES	Frequency (f) (n=11)	Percentage
Leading people	9.8	89.2%
People performance management	10	91%
People development	9.4	85.6%

Table 2 indicated that the leadership competencies of the school heads under people management is high, garnering 91%, while leading people and people management garnered 89.2% and 85.6 % respectively. This implies that the induction program overwhelmingly improves the school heads' capacity in managing people's performance. Thus, it implies that induction programs play an important role in expanding school heads’ conception of performance

management—from compliance monitoring toward developmental supervision—supporting the study’s focus on leadership capacity shaped through induction. Despite a very satisfactory rate in leading people and people management, the result indicates that these two indicators could be emphasized to improve school heads' leadership holistically. Reinforcing the indicator, people development, implied that induction programs should continue strengthening both the strategic and relational components of leadership, as both are central to how leadership is enacted and perceived in school contexts.

Induction program attended by the school heads

This study garnered the salient features of the school heads' induction program attended to establish a comprehensive result.

Table 3: Induction Program Participation and Implementation Levels

Features	Frequency (n=11)	Percentage
Years of Attendance		
2021-2025	2	18.2%
2016-2020	6	54.5%
2004-2015	2	18.2%
Unspecified	1	9.1%
Level of implementation		
Division	6	54.5%
Regional	3	27.3%
District-based	2	18.2%
Others	1	9.1%
Delivery mode		
Face-to-face	11	100%
Duration		
1-10 hours	3	27.3%
21 hours and above	8	72.7%
Components		
Leading strategically	11	100%
Focusing on teaching and learning	10	90.9%
Managing school operations and resources	9	81.8%
Developing self and others	9	81.8%
Building connections	9	81.8%
Others	1	9.1%

Among the 11 participants that responded to this question, induction attendance was most reported within the 2016–2020 group (6; 54.5%), while smaller proportions participated in 2004–2015 (2; 18.2%) and 2021–2025 (2; 18.2%), and one did not specify a year (9.1%). This pattern indicates that induction exposure occurred at different points in time, meaning that some school heads may have attended induction relatively recently while others did so long ago. For the level of implementation, the most frequently reported level was Division (6 selections; 54.5%), followed by Regional (3; 27.3%) and District-based (2; 18.2%), with one mention of Others (1; 9.1%) and no reports for school-based or national levels. This indicates that induction exposure was primarily delivered through intermediate governance levels, especially at the division level. For the study’s purpose, this pattern implies that most induction experiences were likely organized and standardized through division initiatives, which may influence consistency in training content and support mechanisms. All participants reported face-to-face (11; 100%) participation, with no reports of online or blended modes. Most participants reported a duration of 21 hours and above (8; 72.7%), while 3 (27.3%) reported only 1–10 hours, and none reported 11–20 hours. This suggests that when induction was attended, it was often delivered in relatively long training hours, which increases the likelihood of meaningful engagement with training content. The component coverage reported by participants was broad and strongly aligned with leadership domains. All participants indicated Leading Strategically (11; 100%), while very high proportions also attended Focusing on Teaching and Learning (10; 90.9%); Managing School Operations and Resources, Developing Self and Others; and Building Connections (each 9; 81.8%), with one “Others” response (9.1%). This suggests that induction exposure was generally comprehensive rather than limited to only one leadership area. It also implies that any observed strengths or gaps in leadership application across domains may help identify which parts of induction translate more effectively into practice and which domains may require reinforcement through follow-up support.

Experiences of the school heads in the induction program

There were three major themes presented in this study that describes the experiences of the school heads in their participation in the school head’s induction program.

Themes	Description	Sample Responses
Bridging Theory and Practice	The connection between the theoretical knowledge gained from induction programs and practical	"It serves as a bridge of theory and practice." This experience noted that the training provided them with

	applications in school leaders was highlighted. Participants in the induction programs emphasized the significance of bridging the gap between theory and practice.	essential strategies and competencies that they could directly apply in their roles as school heads.
Empowering Leadership through Collaboration	The participants in the school head’s induction program experienced collaborative practices and shared experiences in enhancing leadership capabilities among school heads. This collaborative learning not only built confidence but also created a support network that encouraged ongoing professional development.	“The sharing of experiences wherein we were able to look back at our previous decisions and analyze its results.” The program fostered a collaborative environment where school heads could share their experiences and learn from one another.
Navigating Challenges in Leadership	The program addresses the challenges faced by school heads during their induction training and how these experiences shaped their leadership practices. These challenges prompted them to develop coping strategies and resilience, ultimately enhancing their decision-making skills	"Being a school head is a complex balancing act that involves recognizing and managing people, budget, and educational standards." Participants acknowledged various challenges encountered during the induction programs, such as balancing administrative duties and managing expectations.

Development of a guidebook

While school heads demonstrated high ratings in both core behavioral and leadership competencies, the study identified significant gaps in school heads' induction program experiences along inclusions, content delivery, timing, and program naming; these served as the primary basis for the development of the leadership guidebook. For the development of a guidebook, the content focuses on the core behavioral and leadership competencies of school heads. A detailed and comprehensive framework of the guidebook was developed. Targeting both the key areas garnered high and low scores. The guidebook serves as reinforcement and a tool for enhancement of school heads' core behavioral competencies. A practical goal was included in catering for the leadership competencies. Contents align to the five key domains: Leading Strategically, Focusing on Teaching and Learning, Managing School Operations Resources, Developing Self and Others, and Building Connections of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH). The guidebook was designed as an interactive and user-friendly tool where sample forms, plans, and even the guide computation of part II of the OPCRf were accessible through hard copy and a Quick Response (QR) code directing to a drive where all the needed documents are stored. Furthermore, real life challenges accompanied by actionable tips and potential solutions to assist school heads in navigating complex field scenarios were also included. The suggested features in both the content and design to ensure full compliance with the project's objectives were initiated. Consequently, the feedback and suggestions gathered from the evaluators served as the primary basis for the final refinement of the guidebook.

IV. DISCUSSION

The Leadership Competencies of School Heads

The study reveals that the overall rating of the school heads along core behavioral and leadership competencies was outstanding, which connotes that the exposure of school heads to induction programs greatly improves these competencies. Continuous leadership development is vital in upskilling their leadership skills (Agravante et al., 2023). Therefore, the school heads' induction program should include competencies that directly address leadership needs, context-specific with its relevance and application varying by position, indicating the need for tailored approaches. In core behavioral competencies, sets of behaviors should be improved and lived with maturity. School heads must strengthen their confidence in recognizing their own self-management practices and help align self-perception with stakeholder observation, since leadership development is not only about practice but also about leaders' self-awareness and reflective capacity. School heads should not only promote efficiency in the workplace but also live with it. Nwabuatu (2025) points out that school heads should practice SMART

(Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) goals in planning personal targets and aligning them with the organizational goals. Consequently, creating a positive and productive workplace. Moreover, making personal sacrifices to meet the organization's needs is part of professionalism and ethics. Leading requires personal sacrifices in terms of time and effort, but it does not require martyrdom. School heads must manage their well-being and inspire colleagues to do so. Work with passion while managing your self-worth; by doing so, teachers will be inspired to share their knowledge and talents because they felt they are being taken care of (Su et al., 2022). Additionally, teachers and colleagues translate a supportive environment into commitment; school heads should recognize their importance in empowering teachers and stakeholders in achieving organizational goals (Mariano & Solomon, 2024). Furthermore, school heads must prioritize the organizational goals through minimal mistakes under a results focus. To achieve long-term goals, school heads, teachers, and stakeholders should have mutual understanding of the organizational growth and how these targeted objectives will be efficiently achieved. Continuing monitoring would uplift and improve the organizational performance (Nwabuatu, 2025). According to the study, this indicates that induction-related leadership development may benefit from emphasizing measurable performance management practices (timeliness, output quality, and efficiency) and clarifying performance indicators so school heads can more confidently connect their practices to results-based leadership outcomes. However, even with a clearer view of goals and an organized system of delivery, organizational teamwork holds the key to success. For this study, the results highlight induction's potential role in reinforcing ethical leadership not only as compliance but also as a lived practice recognized by colleagues, supporting the study's aim to understand how induction relates to school heads' leadership competencies. Promoting teamwork is a crucial part of school leadership; however, sustaining the organizational collaborative culture is very challenging, yet if obtained, it will be a stronghold of the organization. School heads should acknowledge the diverse personalities, explore ways to encourage open communication, provide strong support from colleagues, and continue professional growth to widen one's perspectives (Villamor, 2025). Likewise, a school head's service orientation implied an above-satisfactory standard; it suggests that they cultivate a culture of service excellence, a good example for the teachers. School heads must work harder than their teammates and initiate forward thinking and a model of professional stewardship (Ye et al., 2022). Furthermore, translating creative thinking into actual output leads to work improvement. For this study, the implication is that induction may strengthen leadership by helping school heads document, reflect on, and confidently report the concrete innovations they implement—aligning leadership development with

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evidence-based practice. School heads may provide platforms to transform ideas into tangible results and sustain creative thinking (Nasabi et al., 2026). For leadership competencies, the rating under people management was strikingly high, which collaborates with the rating results of the core behavioral competencies. The school heads have been a good example to their colleagues and teachers, promoting a high standard of commitment and collaboration (Ye et al., 2022). The high rating on these domains was consistent with the results of teamwork, a domain in core behavioral competencies. This concludes that school leadership competencies reflect their core behavioral competencies and conversely. For people performance management and people development domains, an average result was noted, although this implies satisfactory performance, and it also yields hidden underperformance competencies that need to be enhanced. According to Rendi et al. (2025), in people's performance management, school heads should empower skills in connecting to teachers, recognizing their strengths and weaknesses to provide timely and meaningful opportunities for growth. Moreover, explore advanced and efficient service delivery that could improve organizational performance. And for people development, which entails thorough enhancement, focus on coaching and mentoring teachers. The study of Thipatdee et al. (2019) states that supporting teachers in their professional growth and exposing them to training that is relevant to their skills and needs will provide a promising result. School heads should have deepened knowledge in various areas to provide effective technical assistance to teachers. Strengthening indicators on people management indicate that induction may be particularly valuable in strengthening school heads' intentional mentoring and coaching competencies and in helping them articulate these practices as part of their leadership attributes—which is important for understanding how induction contributes to leadership development and for informing the design of a relevant output based on study findings.

School Head's Induction Program

The school head's induction program showed inconsistency in terms of opportunity, timing, program naming, content delivery, and strengthened mentorship. This is contrast to the expected delivery of the program, which adheres to improving leadership readiness of school heads along with teaching and organizational culture and provides quality education aligned with the aspects of SDG 4 (Quality Education) (Ortiz et al., 2025). Only eleven school heads attended the induction program, indicating a low participation rate, inconsistent scheduling, and diverse program names emphasizing a lack of standardized timeline and program naming. Despite all PPSSH domains being captured, the variation in depth of content implied a limited program exposure. For the study's purpose, "pattern" implies that most

induction experiences were likely organized and standardized through division initiatives and often delivered in relatively long training hours, which increases the likelihood of meaningful engagement with training. This connotes that there is no district nor school-based induction program that can offer a localized program for school heads. This localized induction program may deliver more specific content that is based on the district or school's needs. Consequently, the data shows that most of the school heads engage in induction programs between 2016 and 2020 (54.5%), while others, around 18.2%, participate in the years 2004 to 2015, and another 18.2% experienced the program years 2021 to 2025. This implies that there were school heads who experienced induction programs as their foundational training, while others already rendered years in service before getting the formal training for school leadership. School head's early years in school management entail support and formal training to face leadership challenges (Bickmore et al., 2021). Additionally, a 100% face-to-face mode of implementation was gathered; this indicates that the school head's induction program remains in the traditional mode of training delivery. With this, long hours of training exposure were recorded, with 72.7 % of 21 hours and above. The training duration and mode of delivery resulted in a deepened content exposure that yielded an "outstanding" rate in the five domains of PPSSH. Domain 1, leading strategically, garnered a 100% content focus, which indicates that school heads can manage their schools well. It also suggests that they can strategize school mandates for better function and services (Barola & Digo, 2022). This program for school heads is a vital part of their holistic progress. Therefore, it should be standardized and structured, comprising all the five domains of PPSSH. According to the Department of Education (2017), the domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017) set the standard for professional development that could support the professional growth of the teachers. Therefore, it is suggested to have an equal opportunity for all school heads within a defined period. Moreover, the experience of the participant in informal mentoring may result in varied mentorship. And a formal mentorship journey is indicated for concise and strategic interpersonal guidance. Experienced school heads may mentor new school heads to develop personal and professional growth and be guided through the real-life challenges of school management (Bobier & Chua, 2025). The induction exposure was generally comprehensive rather than limited to only one leadership area. It also implies that any observed strengths or gaps in leadership application across domains may help identify which parts of induction translate more effectively into practice and which domains may require reinforcement through follow-up support. The school heads' induction program should be a continued and dynamic process rather than a one-time program; it can support not only the entry level of school leadership but also

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the ongoing professional leadership of the school heads. Constant learning is a fundamental aspect for the continuing development of leadership skills (Carcueva & Ureta, 2024). The school head's induction program that is continued and supports the entire and ongoing professional leadership journey of school heads could address every cycle and level of school heads' leadership journey.

Navigating the School Head's Experiences in the Induction Program

The program offered a holistic and transformative approach; it bridges the gaps between theory and practice, fosters collaboration, and develops resiliency in navigating leadership challenges. The core behavioral competencies define the "how" of the leadership delivery of the school heads. The leadership competencies comprise the domains in the PPSSH catered to in the induction program. The study reveals that the induction program helps school heads to apply theoretical concepts to real-world school management challenges; school expectations were faced, and gained professional resiliency was gained. One school head shared, "It serves as a bridge of theory and practice." This experience noted that the training provided them with essential strategies and competencies that they could directly apply in their roles as school heads. Another school head mentioned, "The training leads me to deepen my understanding of leadership and how I smoothly discharge my task." The program entails an opportunity to apply concepts into the leadership field, whereas it provides guidance and a clearer view of leadership practice and strategies (Agravante et al., 2023b). Through the program collaboration, where emphasized and nurtured, shared responsibility and feedback among participants indicate program success. It was mentioned, "The sharing of experiences wherein we were able to look back at our previous decisions and analyze their results." The program serves as an outlet of strategic experimentation wherein a series of leadership challenges and experiences were catered to review and analyze. Real-life experiences can improve a school head's strategic skills and basis for future setbacks along with school management (Barola & Digo, 2022). It also offers opportunities to foresee challenges and possible solutions through program tools and strategies; mentorship that guides fellow school heads creates a lifelong learner (Brooks, 2017). Moreover, the program must intensify coaching and mentoring; it will allow experienced and new school heads to work collaboratively and each share their own leadership identities. As stated by a school head, "The most valuable element of the program is coaching and mentoring." The program acknowledges the vital role of coaching and mentoring, especially for new school heads who still consult their superior or their former mentor for guidance in their leadership journey (Arrieta & Ancho, 2020). Furthermore, school management does not only surround itself with decision-making or teaching and learning delivery, but it also

captures financial management and managing people. The program prepares or reinforces the school heads with the skills needed. As mentioned by the school head, "Being a school head is a complex balancing act that recognizes managing people, budget, and educational standards." The management of allotted school funds or the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) requires intensive planning and financial-related skills such as budgeting and fund sourcing to handle the financial challenges of the school (Amado et al., 2025). The induction program provides background and legal basis to prepare school heads in handling such sensitive responsibility. As supported by the school head, "I felt more confident and was guided on the processes and activities in school management." The various faces of leadership development and the experiential learning in the induction program provide a promising tool in facing school management challenges. Therefore, induction programs of school heads should strengthen practical applications, mentorship, and continued support and feedback for professional and leadership development.

Guidebook Development

This study proposed a guidebook that could bridge the gap in the implementation of school heads' induction programs to improve the core behavioral and leadership competencies. The school heads' induction program was commonly defined as the "bridge" stage of leadership, preparing new school heads from classroom setups into the world of school leadership. It is important that the school heads are exposed to specific professional assistance to reach the next stage of competence (Patiga, 2025). However, the result implied that the "school heads induction program" was not consistently delivered and available to the identified groups of school heads, resulting in tried skills in leadership endeavors. The proposed guidebook offered the flexibilities of the program that can strengthen school leadership practices (Semblante & Sambo, 2025). Its content is aligned to the five domains of the PPSSH, focusing on the core behavioral and leadership competencies of school heads derived from part II of their Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRF). Equal opportunity for all school heads will be assured; on-time leadership competencies will be achieved that may result in well-developed leadership skills. Through this guidebook school leadership competencies can be enhanced anywhere and anytime, which offers an interactive learning experience using Quick Response (QR) codes. This will improve the digital skills of the school heads and create a positive response along with digitalization (Foster & Digo, 2024). Moreover, the identified less developed core behavioral and leadership competencies will be focused on, resulting in an even more developed leadership competency for its user. To intensify coaching and mentoring, the guidebook will provide real scenarios on school leadership and actionable tips on handling such challenges. Standardized

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forms and sample plans will be available for the rating computation for part II of the OPCR. These features of the guidebook, along with mentorship and coaching, will provide guidance and continue professional growth (Palacio & Digo, 2024). The guidebook will adhere to its purpose, to enhance the core behavioral and leadership competencies of school heads. And strengthen inclusion for a better form of leadership, whereas school heads were much more ready and equipped on their first day of school leadership.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn: (1) The induction program of school heads has a direct impact on school heads' performance along core behavioral and leadership competencies. (2). The induction program for school heads has been inconsistently implemented, resulting in limited participation. (3) The content of the school head's induction program should be compliant with the PPSSH domains to ensure the improvement of the core behavioral and leadership competencies of the school heads. (4) The proposed guidebook should cater to the core behavioral and leadership competencies that should be accessible to all target users.

Based on the conclusion, school heads should use the guidebook to develop and reinforce leadership competencies. For the Schools Division Office, institutionalize the use of the guidebook to bridge the gap in inclusion, and it will serve as complementary material for the school heads' induction program to ensure school heads' readiness in school management. For the policymakers, it includes real-life scenarios on school management and strengthens mentoring and coaching for future professional development training for school heads, as it is noted as effective. And for other researchers, conduct a future study on the long-term effects of the guidebook in enhancing core behavioral and leadership competencies of school heads.

VI. DISCLOSURE

We declare that we have no financial or material interests related to the research in this paper that could create a conflict of interest.

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